

A STUDY ON THE SATISFACTION LEVEL TOWARDS ONLINE LEARNING WITH RESPECT TO UNDER-GRADUATE STUDENTS OF DOMBIVLI CITY

Ms. Shruti S. Bhosle, **Ms. Prachi N. Jadhav And *Ms. Prerna O. Singh*

Assistant Professor, K.V. Pendharkar College (Autonomous), Dombivli, India.

Abstract :

The online education system is new normal for the students as well as teachers. COVID-19 has impacted all the sectors; the education sector is no exception to it. Due to pandemics schools and colleges shifted to online platforms. The study focused on the satisfaction level of undergraduate students during the pandemic. The study states that students preferred offline mode over online because virtual learning fails to enhance their skills such as communications skills, interpersonal skills, the ability of critical thinking etc. The study also analysed that students' mental health was affected because of online lecture schedules and their concentration power was adversely impacted. Due to online learning, the practical approach was compromised.

Key words: *Interaction, Online self-efficacy, Online-learning, Self-motivation and Satisfaction.*

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Introduction :

We can trace back the roots of the ancient Indian education system to the Vedic period. The education was based on the Gurukul system. Ancient India was famous for its universities such as Nalanda and Taxila. Interaction and discussions were an important part of the ancient education system. Modern education which was introduced by Britishers' still influences our education system. New Education Policy aims to bring a practical approach. COVID - 19 introduced e-learning which is providing education to students during this critical period. Students are getting knowledge from their homes, but it is adversely affecting the practical approach of students. If we want to achieve the overall development of the students we have to focus on a practical approach towards education and we can provide that through hybrid mode. In the present time, students' mental health and skills improvement are key issues. Developing countries faced the problem of technical infrastructure.

Review of Literature :

1. T. Muthuprasad, S. Aishwarya, K.S. Aditya, Girish K. Jha (2021), This study understands agricultural students' perception and preference towards online learning. This study focused on improvement in student's effectiveness,

hybrid mode of education and network connectivity issues which are faced by under developing countries like India.

2. Sumitra Pokhrel, Roshan Chhetri (2021) This study highlights the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning. It focuses on the need of the hour to innovate and implement alternative educational systems and assessment strategies. It also emphasizes learning and teaching during a pandemic.
3. Kunal Chaturvedi, Dinesh Kumar Vishwakarma and Nidhi Singh (2020). This paper throws light on students' mental health and their daily routine which is affected due to pandemics. This Study focused on the hybrid model of education. This paper highlights new policies and guidelines that will help to reduce negative effects and prepare teachers and students for the future health crisis.
4. Shahiba EC(2020) A study on the student's satisfaction towards online classes in the Covid 19 pandemic situation with special reference to school students of Malappuram district. This study shows that online learning programmes provide more information to the students but still we cannot replace a teacher and their relationship in classroom teaching. Teaching is just replaced by learning through active participation and interaction. It's been concluded that the e-learning approach, which mixes self-paced learning, live online learning and face-to-face classroom learning has the capability of up action of the scholars.

Objectives of the Study :

1. To understand the satisfaction level of students towards online learning system
2. To understand the factors influencing online learning system
3. To understand the students' opinion towards the preferred way of learning.

Hypothesis :

1. H_0 - There is no significant association between gender and a convenient mode of education.
 H_1 - There is a significant association between gender and a convenient mode of education.
2. H_0 - There is no significant association between discipline and convenient mode of education.
 H_1 - There is a significant association between discipline and convenient mode of education.

Scope of the Study :

The study is focused on satisfaction levels among undergraduate students in the online mode of learning. It also emphasizes students' understanding due to the backdrop of online learning. It also analyses the role of gender and stream in determining the satisfaction level of students and examines the influence of interaction, self-motivation on their academics. It throws light on students' participation in MOOC courses.

Research Methodology :

Primary data is collected through a Google form. This study has collected data from undergraduate students of different disciplines. The structured questionnaire method is used for collecting the data of 298 respondents from Dombivli city.

Tools and Techniques Used for Analysis :

The Chi-square test is used for statistical analysis.

Limitations of the study :

1. The study is restricted only to Dombivli city.
2. The study is limited to only undergraduate students.
3. Time and Resource Constraint.

Research Analysis :

Table 1:

Sr.No	Data analysis	Attributes	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Gender	Male	146	49.00
		Female	152	51.00
2	Discipline	Arts	82	27.50
		Science	80	26.80
		Commerce	136	45.60
3	Convenient mode of education	Online	117	39.30
		Offline	181	60.70
4	Time for Self-preparation during online education	Yes	240	80.50
		No	58	19.50
5	Practical's effected	Adversely affected	93	31.20
		Moderately affected	128	43.00
		Not at all effected	43	14.40
		Favourably affected	34	11.40
6	Interaction with college friends	Never	38	12.80
		Rarely	90	30.20
		Sometimes	115	38.60
		Often	24	8.10
		Always	31	10.40

7	Awareness About MOOC	Yes	128	43.00
		No	170	57.00
	Teacher's motivation for MOOC Courses	Yes	120	40.27
		No	178	49.73
	Enrolled for a MOOC Course during Pandemic	Yes	87	29.20
		No	211	70.80

(Source - Primary data)

Table 1 shows that 49% are male and the remaining are female. The table indicates 27.5 % of respondents are from the Arts stream, 26.8% are from the Science stream and 45.6% are from the Commerce stream. 39.3% of Students preferred the online mode of education and 60.7% preferred the offline mode of education. It analysed that students preferred the offline mode of education over the online mode. From the above table, it examined that during the online mode of education students get more time for self-preparation as compared to the offline mode of education. It indicated that the overall attributes are 100% under this, 31.20% of students' practical's were adversely affected and 43.00% of students were moderately affected. It explained the importance of practical effects due to online education mode. The above table indicates that during online learning students do not interact as much with their friends as they are used to doing in offline education mode. From the above data, it analysed that due to the online mode of education most of the students are satisfied, but we can also see that some of them are not at all satisfied because of connectivity issues while attending the classes. Due to this, most of the students were moderately satisfied with the learning environment at home. To put it differently, it explained the online mode is not that satisfactory to the students. Through offline mode of education students can solve their doubts. Hence, we can conclude that the online mode of education is moderately satisfactory to the students. Thousands of MOOCs are available online, but many are offered on popular platforms, and by institutions that have invested in making their courses accessible online. Each module typically includes a combination of lectures, readings, interactive graphics and diagrams, problem sets and a quiz or test at the end. But the above table shows that only 29.20% of students enrolled on MOOC courses during the pandemic.

Table 2: Students skills are affected / improved due to online education

Sr No	Skills	Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good	Excellent
1	Communication Skill	81	94	85	23	15
2	Interpersonal Skill	57	120	85	22	14
3	Techno Savvy	43	86	96	46	27
4	Critical thinking and problem solving	57	94	85	39	23

(Source - Primary data)

The frequency and percentage were calculated for each of the four statements rated on a scale of the five-point continuum as shown in Table 2. From the above data, it examined that because of online education mode students were more aware of technology, but their communication skills, interpersonal skills, critical thinking and problem-solving ability are not as much improved during the online education mode.

Table 3 : Hypothesis Testing

Result of Chi-Square Test :

Calculate Value	Table Value	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance
4.27	3.8414	1	5%

The calculated value of Chi-square is 4.27 which is greater than the critical value of 3.8414 at 5 degrees of freedom and 95% level of confidence. The critical value is lesser than the calculated value therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in gender and the convenient mode of education.

Calculate Value	Table Value	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance
83.82	5.99146	2	5%

The calculated value of Chi-square is 83.82 which is greater than the critical value of 5.99146 at 5 degrees of freedom and 95% level of confidence. The critical value is lesser than the calculated value therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Since it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the discipline and the convenient mode of education.

Findings :

1. Most of the students preferred the offline mode of education rather than the online mode of education.
2. Most of the students responded that their practical's were moderately affected due to the online mode of education.
3. Doubt solving and interaction with teachers was comparatively less in an online education learning system.
4. Due to the online education mode of learning students get much familiar with technical devices.
5. Our study found that due to online learning students are aware of MOOCs and they started enrolling for the same.
6. From this study, we also analyse students' mental health affected by online mode of education.

Suggestions :

1. Teachers should provide maximum attention to all the students. Proper training of educators for digital skills and improved student-teacher interaction must be conducted.
2. Colleges should take initiative to provide good infrastructure to the students for online lectures.
3. Teachers should create awareness about MOOC among students and they need to motivate them to join MOOC.
4. To make online education more interesting we can conduct activities like poster making, quiz competitions, workshops on personality development etc.

5. Due to the online education model, students' mental health is affected, to improve students' mental health as teachers need to listen to students' concerns and understand them, offering them to have one to one conversations.

Conclusion :

The entire education system was greatly affected by the Covid-19 Pandemic. Online education offers students the opportunity to study at their own pace. Although it provides various opportunities to students, still, it will be disastrous to replace the offline education system with the online education system. Online education mode fails to provide a practical approach. This study concluded that the hybrid mode of education is a better option for the students during the pandemic. This study mainly focused on students' satisfaction towards online education but students were moderately satisfied with the online education system.

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